

A surreal Nucleosynthesis

Chemical Elements are presented as numerical admixtures of Hydrogen, Deuterium, and Tritium

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In the beginning was (no, not that) **H**ydrogen.

We've known for over century that the **H**ydrogen atom is electrically neutral and comprised of a (positive) **P**roton and a (negative) **e**lectron. Since the sixties [1] the Proton is known to be a Tri**Q**uark; the constituents are termed (very creatively!) Up(**u**) and Down(**d**). In terms of charges

$$q(\mathbf{u}) = 2/3$$

$$q(\mathbf{d}) = -1/3$$

fractionality needed to yield

$$\text{Proton} = \{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{d}\} \Rightarrow q(\mathbf{P}) = 1$$

and counter the negative charge carried by the **e**lectron; thus

$$q(\mathbf{H}) = q(\mathbf{P}) + q(\mathbf{e}) = 0$$

Notice the absence of a **N**eutron; who ordered that particle, as I. I. Rabi might ask? James Chadwick, in 1932! Here he is, in Rutherford's 1920 Physics Research Class, 2nd row, first on left; in the same row is Arthur Compton, of the 'Compton' Effect fame, second from right; both eventual residents in the Manhattan District.

Physics Research Students, June 1920.

Actually, if instead

$$q(\mathbf{u}) = 1$$

$$q(\mathbf{d}) = -1$$

then also

$$\mathbf{Proton} = \{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{d}\} \Rightarrow q(\mathbf{P}) = 1$$

but this is problematic; for the 'eventual' **N**eutron:

$$\mathbf{Neutron} = \{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}\} \Rightarrow q(\mathbf{N}) = -1$$

contradicted by observation and its very name; of course, making the Neutron a Quad**Q**uark would work.

Now, for a **N**eutron to emerge, one of the Up **Q**uarks inside a **P**roton must lose a full charge; since

$$q(\mathbf{u}) - 1 = q(\mathbf{d})$$

then

$$\mathbf{Neutron} = \{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}\} \Rightarrow q(\mathbf{N}) = 0$$

This is really where the bizarre idea of fractional charges becomes a necessity.

Hydrogen itself could be a **N**eutron generator via 'charge-meld':

$$\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{P} + \mathbf{e} = \{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{d}\} + \mathbf{e} \Rightarrow \{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{d}, \mathbf{d}\} = \mathbf{N}$$

An almost magical way to make **N**eutrons from **H**ydrogen!

Unfortunately, free **N**eutrons decay back to **P**rotons and **e**lectrons in about 15 minutes, and free **P**rotons take an eternity to decay. Nucleosynthesis must involve more than one **H**ydrogen atom; and then the Strong Force will obligingly allow 'charge-meld' to work.

Deutirium

This atom is **H**ydrogen with a **N**eutron:

$$\mathbf{H}_2 = \mathbf{H} + \mathbf{N} = \mathbf{P} + \mathbf{e} + \mathbf{N}$$

Let's fuse two **H**ydrogen atoms:

$$2\mathbf{H} = 2\mathbf{P} + 2\mathbf{e} = \{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{d}\} + \mathbf{e} + \{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{d}\} + \mathbf{e}$$

As we know, a **N**eutron will emerge when one of the Up-**Q**uarks inside one of the **P**rotons loses a full charge; which one is chosen at random, it would seem; and the Strong Force confines the 'charge-meld' to only one **P**roton. The 'meld' (in red) yields

$$\mathbf{H}_2 = \{2/3, 2/3, -1/3\} + \{-1\} + \{2/3, 2/3, -1/3\} + \{-1\} = \mathbf{P} + \mathbf{e} + \mathbf{N} = \mathbf{H} + \mathbf{N}$$

the desired result.

But, what has become of the leftover 'chargeless' **e**lectron? Is there such a thing? Did its energy just 'photonize'?

Did this 'electron' instead collapse into the Up-Quark altogether? By what process? There's also the matter of mass; the Up-Quark has $2.4\text{MeV}/c^2$, the Down-Quark has $4.8\text{MeV}/c^2$ while the electron has only $.5\text{MeV}/c^2$. Where is the missing mass?

Tritium

This dangerous atom is comprised of Deuterium plus a Neutron:

$$\mathbf{H_3 = H_2 + N = P + e + 2N}$$

To get here by the 'meld' method, let's fuse 3 Hydrogen atoms:

$$\mathbf{3H = 3P + 3e = \{u,u,d\} + e + \{u,u,d\} + e + \{u,u,d\} + e}$$

so now we know the drill (two 'melds' here):

$$\mathbf{H_3 = \{2/3,2/3,-1/3\} + \{-1\} + \{2/3,2/3,-1/3\} + \{-1\} + \{2/3,2/3,-1/3\} + \{-1\}}$$

Helium

This atom is comprised of two Protons, two electrons, and two Neutron; thus

$$\mathbf{He = 2P + 2e + 2N = 2H + 2N}$$

Now that Deuterium is available after fusing two Hydrogen atoms and executing a 'meld'

$$\mathbf{H_2 = P + e + N}$$

just fuse two such atoms:

$$\mathbf{He = 2H_2 = 2P + 2e + 2N = H + H_3}$$

Lithium

The makeup here is

$$\mathbf{Li = 3P + 3e + 3N}$$

Bootstrapping directly from Deuterium would certainly work:

$$\mathbf{Li = 3H_2}$$

Thus Deuterium would seem to be the agent of nucleosynthesis; but Hydrogen is in over-abundance, not Deuterium.

Let's try fusing three Hydrogen atoms directly:

$$\mathbf{3H = \{2/3,2/3,-1/3\} + \{-1\} + \{2/3,2/3,-1/3\} + \{-1\} + \{2/3,2/3,-1/3\} + \{-1\}}$$

One 'charge-meld' as before (in red) doesn't work by itself:

$$\mathbf{Li(1) = \{2/3,2/3,-1/3\} + \{-1\} + \{2/3,2/3,-1/3\} + \{-1\} + \{2/3,2/3,-1/3\} + \{-1\}}$$

$$\mathbf{Li(1) \Rightarrow 2P + 2e + N = H + H_2}$$

As above, two 'charge-melds' in addition yields Tritium

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{H_3} &= \{2/3, 2/3, -1/3\} + \{-1\} + \{2/3, 2/3, -1/3\} + \{-1\} + \{2/3, 2/3, -1/3\} + \{-1\} \\ &= \mathbf{P + e + 2N} \end{aligned}$$

so now the Lithium atom follows arithmetically (and very neatly):

$$\mathbf{Li = H + H_2 + H_3}$$

Let's do one last example:

Beryllium

$$\mathbf{Be = 4P + 4e + 4N}$$

This time it seems more choices are available.

1) Fuse two Hydrogen atoms to get Deuterium and then:

$$\mathbf{Be = 4H_2}$$

2) Fuse four Hydrogen atoms and do one 'charge-meld':

$$\mathbf{Be(1) = \{2/3, 2/3, -1/3\} + \{-1\} + \{2/3, 2/3, -1/3\} + \{-1\} + \{2/3, 2/3, -1/3\} + \{-1\} + \{2/3, 2/3, -1/3\} + \{-1\}}$$

to get

$$\mathbf{Be(1) \Rightarrow 3P + 3e + N = 3H + N = 2H + H_2}$$

Then separately do 3 'charge-melds' on four Hydrogen atoms:

$$\mathbf{Be(2) = \{2/3, 2/3, -1/3\} + \{-1\} + \{2/3, 2/3, -1/3\} + \{-1\} + \{2/3, 2/3, -1/3\} + \{-1\} + \{2/3, 2/3, -1/3\} + \{-1\}}$$

to get

$$\mathbf{Be(2) \Rightarrow P + e + 3N = H + N + 2N = H_2 + 2N = H_3 + N}$$

and arithmetic carries the day once more:

$$\mathbf{Be = Be(1) + Be(2) = H + 2H_2 + H_3}$$

3) Fuse four Hydrogen atoms and do two 'charge-meld':

$$\mathbf{Be(2) = \{2/3, 2/3, -1/3\} + \{-1\} + \{2/3, 2/3, -1/3\} + \{-1\} + \{2/3, 2/3, -1/3\} + \{-1\} + \{2/3, 2/3, -1/3\} + \{-1\}}$$

to get

$$\mathbf{Be(2) \Rightarrow 2P + 2e + 2N}$$

so then

$$\mathbf{Be = 2Be(2)}$$

All this has led to the realization that the atomic Trinity $\{H, H_2, H_3\}$ may be used (if no more than just numerically) to build the Elements in the Table. First recall that

$$H_2 = H + N$$

$$H_3 = H_2 + N = H + 2N$$

The atomic number (Proton counter) π will connect to scalings of Trinity members. First

$$H(1) = H + 0H_2 + 0H_3$$

not suprizing since Hydrogen is already part of the Club. For atomic numbers $\pi > 1$, an element $EL(\pi)$ with atomic number π becomes (very neatly) the admixture

$$EL(\pi) = aH + bH_2 + aH_3$$

so obviously

$$\pi = 2a + b$$

for positive integers a, b ; this is akin to partitioning a positive integer into a sum of integer neighbors differing by no more than one.

Here are a few elements; shorthand sgnatures in parens, Deuterium scaler in red:

$$He(2) = H + 0H_2 + H_3 (101)$$

$$Li(3) = H + H_2 + H_3 (111)$$

$$C(6) = 2H + 2H_2 + 2H_3 (222)$$

$$N(7) = 2H + 3H_2 + 2H_3 (232)$$

$$O(8) = 3H + 2H_2 + 3H_3 (323)$$

$$Au(79) = 26H + 27H_2 + 26H_3 (262726)$$

$$Pb(82) = 27H + 28H_2 + 27H_3 (272827)$$

$$U(92) = 31H + 30H_2 + 31H_3 (313031)$$

$$Pu(94) = 31H + 32H_2 + 31H_3 (313231)$$

$$Es(99) = 33H + 33H_2 + 33H_3 (333333)$$

How does this reset the Periodic Table? A next article will proppse radical changes.

References

[1] George Zweig: "Discovering Quarks", Cambridge University Press, 2025, p. 79.